

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It gives me great pleasure to announce the fourth regular issue of 2023. I would like to thank all the authors for their sound research papers and the editorial board and our guest reviewers for their extremely valuable reviews and suggestions for improvement. These contributions and the generous support of the consortium members enable us to run our journal and maintain its quality. I would also like to thank our broader community for reading and incorporating sound J.UCS papers into their research.

Still, I would like to expand our editorial board: If you are a tenured associate professor or above with a good publication record, please apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in receiving high-quality proposals for special issues on new topics and emerging trends.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce five accepted papers involving 14 authors from four different countries.

Seyedeh Mahsa Mirhoseini-Moghaddam, Mohammad Reza Yamaghani and Adel Bakhshipour from Iran look into fraud detection for Olive oil by applying smell and sight sensors resulting in an accurate, fast and non-destructive detection of adulteration in extra virgin olive oil. Fahimeh Ramazankhani, Mahdi Yazdian-Dehkordi and Mehdi Rezaeian report their research on kinship verification by analysing facial features based on various texture and color features and metric learning methods. Stefan Strydom, Andrei Michael Dreyer and Brink van der Merwe from South Africa contribute in their research to the International Classification of Disease (ICD) coding based on a transformer model applied to hospital discharge summaries. Fernando Terroso-Saenz and Andres Muñoz from Spain present their research on human mobility prediction using a long short-term memory and Gated Recurrent Unit neural network based on geo-data from cellular phones combined with data from road traffic sensors. Shefali Varshney, Rajinder Sandhu and P. K. Gupta from India report their research on cost-effective scheduling in fog computing based on the modified PROMETHEE technique.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor

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